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A SURVEY ON SECURITY CHALLENGES OF VIRTUALIZATION TECHNOLOGY IN CLOUD COMPUTING

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ABSTRACT

Virtualization has become a widely and attractive employed technology in cloud computing environments. Sharing of a single physical machine between multiple isolated virtual machines leading to a more optimized hardware usage, as well as make the migration and management of a virtual system more efficiently than its physical counterpart. Virtualization is a fundamental technology in a cloud environment. However, the presence of an additional abstraction layer among software and hardware causes new security issues. Security issues related to virtualization technology have become a significant concern for organizations due to arising some new security challenges.

This paper aims to identify the main challenges and risks of virtualization in cloud computing environments. Furthermore, it focuses on some common virtual-related threats and attacks affect the security of cloud computing.

The survey was conducted to obtain the views of the cloud stakeholders on virtualization vulnerabilities, threats, and approaches that can be used to overcome them.

Finally, we propose recommendations for improving security, and mitigating risks encounter virtualization that necessary to adopt secure cloud computing.

KEYWORDS

Cloud Computing, Virtualization, Security, Challenge, Risk

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DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF A RASPBERRY-PI BASED HOME SECURITY AND FIRE SAFETY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Fire alarms and building security systems are currently separate systems and are liable to monthly fees. Video recording for closed-circuit television (CCTV) is done locally subsequently requiring high storage space. Whenever there is a break-in, the footage records can be stolen consequently losing data. To address high data storage space, monthly premium subscriptions, cost of separate systems and data loss issues of the aforementioned systems, we design and implement a Raspberry-pi based fire and intrusion detection systems in this work. The system sends an SMS in the case of an intrusion or fire detection, and then records and uploads the surveillance videos. The system used a GSM modem for sending SMSs, a video, a PIR sensor to detect motion and a smoke or heat sensor to detect fire. The system is a low cost combined home security and fire detection Raspberry-pi system intended for home and small offices use.

KEYWORDS

Raspberry-Pi, PIR, GSM, Security

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